

ΕΕΙΣΟ

European University

EVALUATION OF JOINT ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES

Deliverable 7.4

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP7 – “Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”, as deliverable D7.4 “Evaluation of joint entrepreneurial activities” of the project EELISA INNOVation and COmmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811. D7.4 is a follow-up deliverable of D7.3 “EELISA entrepreneurship action plan” that was submitted in May 2023.

This deliverable (7.4) provides an evaluation of the joint entrepreneurship activities carried out during the implementation phase of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan (D7.3) between June 2023 and May 2024. The EELISA entrepreneurship action plan is a concept for increasing the outreach of entrepreneurial activities across EELISA to different target groups and rests on three pillars: Firstly, an EELISA landscape of startup support that gives an overview of the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at all EELISA partner institutions along all three different stages of the startup journey: nucleation, incubation, and acceleration; secondly, the sharing of those key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at all EELISA partner institutions along all stages of the startup journey wherever possible and meaningful; and thirdly, the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative. The EELISA entrepreneurship action plan has already outlined these three pillars and was implemented in the third year of the EELISA InnoCORE project. **In this deliverable these joint entrepreneurship activities will be evaluated with a preliminary outcome evaluation: We have tracked the outcomes of the actions and are now in a position to draw a preliminary evaluation of the success of the measures (e. g. number of events and consultations, startups generated, funding and venture capital acquired). In summary, it is safe to say that the joint EELISA entrepreneurship activities have been a great success with a very high demand particularly for the new EELISA entrepreneurship activities, i.e., the EELISA Entrepreneurship School and EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event, and will be continued as far as possible in EELISA phase II in WP10.**

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Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Innovation Talks. EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology and innovation for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. EELISA Innovation Talks are an event series set up by EELISA InnoCORE.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 45 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project,

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 General Considerations

In the EELISA InnoCORE Grant Agreement, deliverable 7.4 is laconically described as an “[e]valuation of joint entrepreneurial activities with a preliminary outcome evaluation”. The joint entrepreneurial activities to be evaluated are those of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan that was developed to implement task 7.2 (“Create an infrastructure of business incubators across EELISA”) and task 7.3 (“Implementing an EELISA-wide start-up initiative”). The main objective of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan that was submitted as deliverable (D7.3) and milestone of EELISA InnoCORE WP7 (MS7) in May 2023 was to develop “a concept for increasing the outreach of entrepreneurial activities across EELISA to different target groups”. The EELISA entrepreneurship action plan was implemented from June 2023 to May 2024 and consists of three pillars to be considered for the evaluation in this deliverable:

1. The first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan (D7.3) is an EELISA landscape of startup support that gives an overview about the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at each EELISA partner institution along all three stages of the startup journey: nucleation, incubation, and acceleration. In this EELISA landscape of startup support we have indicated which of our key startup support resources are English-speaking and open to EELISA and which ones are not. The EELISA landscape of startup support has been particularly useful in the implementation of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan in three ways: Firstly, it provided a very useful overview that served well for presenting the EELISA landscape of startup support to internal and external stakeholders in just two figures which can be found on page 71 and 72 of D7.3 and which are replicated here:

EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part A: Key Startup Support Institutions and Services

NUCLEATION	INCUBATION	ACCELERATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UPM CAIT (UPM) • FAU Startup Service (FAU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actúaupm Network of Investors and Experts (UPM) • ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU) • JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab (FAU) • Medical Valley (FAU) • ITU Cekirdek (ITU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU) • JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab (FAU) • Medical Valley (FAU) • JoTTO (SSSA) • Third Mission Administrative Area (SSSA)
OPEN TO EELISA		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurship Group UPM (UPM) • UPM Partnership with Banco Santander (UPM) • Makerspace (ENPC) • Fablab Descartes (ENPC) • FAU Digital Tech Academy (FAU) • ITU GINOVA (ITU) • Knowledge Transfer Office (SNS) • JoTTO Office (SNS) • Contamination Lab (SNS) • Start Cup Toscana 2023 (SSSA) • UPBizz Entrepreneurship Center (UPB) • BME US(3) (BME) • Technology Transfer Services at PSL (PSL) • Mines Paris – PSL coworking space (PSL) • PSL-Lab (PSL coworking space) (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 4 actúaupm (UPM) • Entrepreneurship Group UPM (UPM) • UPM Partnership with Banco Santander (UPM) • Incubateur Descartes (ENPC) • d.school Paris (ENPC) • Station F (ENPC) • Co-Innovation Lab ENPC (ENPC) • NKubator (FAU) • LZE (FAU) • EXISTENCY (FAU) • Agreement and collaboration with POLO TECNOLOGICO NAVACCHIO (SNS) • JUMP (SSSA) • Innovation Labs (UPB) • BME US(3) (BME) • Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL) • PC Up (PSL) • Chimie Paris Innov (PSL) • PSL Tech Seed (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspiring women (UPM) • EXISTENCY (UPM) • ITU ARI teknozent (ITU) • Innovation Labs (UPB) • PSL Innovation Fund (PSL)
NOT OPEN TO EELISA OR NOT ENGLISH-SPEAKING		

Figure 1: EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part A: Key Startup Support Institutions and Services

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EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part B: Key Startup Support Programs and Courses

NUCLEATION	INCUBATION	ACCELERATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • actuaupm (UPM) • Introduction to Intra/Social Entrepreneurship (UPM) • Starting Business Ideas @FAU (FAU) • Technology transfer in nanotechnologies: IP protection, spin-offs (SNS) • High Tech Entrepreneurship Course (SSSA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical Valley Services for Startups (FAU) • ITU SEED Acceleration Program (ITU) • BME US(3) (BME) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical Valley Services for Startups (FAU)
OPEN TO EELISA		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAU Digital Tech Fellows Program (FAU) • Impact(3) (FAU) • Entrepreneurship Bootcamp (from UPBizz) (UPB) • Grand Challenges Scholars Program (from UPBizz) (UPB) • BME's Business Express Program (BME) • The PSL-Pépite entrepreneurship training program (PSL) • PSL-Teams (entrepreneurship awareness program) (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 4 training (UPM) • UPM TT Course (UPM) • d.school Paris: Programme ME310 (ENPC) • ZOLLHOF Talent Program (FAU) • ZOLLHOF Startup Incubation Program (FAU) • EXISTENCY Reality Bites (FAU) • Innovation Labs Hackathon and Pre-Acceleration Phases (UPB) • Incubation Programs at the Incubator Paris-Dauphine (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EXISTENCY Professionalize Program (in cooperation with ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator) (FAU) • Innogate International Acceleration Program (ITU) • Innovation Labs Demo Day and Long-Term Support (UPB) • PSL Tech Acceleration (PSL)
NOT OPEN TO EELISA OR NOT ENGLISH-SPEAKING		

Figure 2: EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part B: Key Startup Support Programs and Courses

What is even more, it also helped to identify these relevant stakeholders in the first place and to think about possible interconnections and new opportunities. The EELISA landscape of startup support also proved extremely useful for the onboarding of our internal and external stakeholders and for showing them the capacities and the potential of our alliance with regard to startup support. Furthermore, it greatly helped for planning new EELISA entrepreneurship activities that were until the beginning of the implementation of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan in June 2023 not yet offered. Secondly, the EELISA landscape of startup support served as a basis for the EELISA InnoCORE webpage on innovation and entrepreneurship that will be highlighted in more detail below. Thirdly, the EELISA landscape of startup support greatly helped to broaden the outreach of our activities: The Second EELISA Prototype Contest and EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event were opened to all startups from the incubators connected to EELISA institutions that were for the first time listed on the EELISA landscape of startup support which helped to increase the number of applicants for these activities and also contributed to their success. In itself, however, the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan, i. e., the EELISA landscape of startup support, was already provided in the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan (cf. esp. pp. 70 f. of D7.3) and in itself constitutes no entrepreneurial activity that – beyond the comments already made – could be further evaluated here.

2. The second pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan is the sharing of our respective key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses along all stages of the startup journey. This second pillar consists of seven components, several of which are

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relevant to be taken into consideration for the present evaluation of joint entrepreneurial activities:

Firstly, the creation of the EELISA landscape of startup support, developed in the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan, already served as a first way of sharing our key startup support resources. There has been the permanent opportunity to update this EELISA landscape of startup support by adding new or deleting old key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses. However, from June 2023 to May 2024 there have been no changes that would have called for a revised version of our EELISA landscape of startup support. In the future, it seems to be useful to extend the EELISA landscape of startup support under EELISA phase II WP10 to include ZHAW and to update it with regard to all institutions on a regular basis. From the perspective of the present deliverable, however, the creation of the EELISA landscape of startup support in itself does not constitute an entrepreneurial activity that would call for an evaluation beyond the comments already made above.

Secondly, as can be already seen from the EELISA landscape of startup support, we have opened several key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses for all EELISA partner institutions. This offered several new entrepreneurship activities to our startups and founders that will be part of the evaluation of our entrepreneurship activities in the following chapter of this deliverable.

Thirdly, we intended to interlink our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses as meaningfully as possible with two aims in mind: On the one hand, startup support resources should be strategically reallocated (in the long run) to avoid duplicate structures wherever possible, to use our resources where they are needed the most, and to further strengthen existing capacities. On the other hand, interlinking our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses would allow our institutions to learn from each other, to exchange best practices, and to benefit from complementary strengths and resources. Since the intention to interlink our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses found its strongest expression in the startup activities itself that we either opened to EELISA or newly created, the evaluation that will follow in the next chapter of this deliverable will keep this aspect of a meaningful interlinkage in the evaluation of our concrete joint entrepreneurial activities – be they opened to EELISA or newly created – in mind.

Fourthly, we promoted our entrepreneurship activities via EELISA media channels for innovation that were developed in D7.5 that was submitted in May 2022. The event organizers had to send the event information to the EELISA Communication Office, which created an event webpage, which was then communicated via EELISA InnoCORE WP1 to the EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives and to the contact points of the EELISA partners' local media channels for innovation (who had been introduced to the procedure in a meeting on 7 July 2022), so that the events could be promoted in a targeted manner in all EELISA partner institutions. WP7 representatives knew about all events and were responsible for overseeing the promotion at their institutions. The events were also announced in the event section on

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the EELISA website. The simultaneous and target group specific promotion of entrepreneurship activities at all EELISA institutions and the incubators connected to EELISA institutions was crucial for getting students, startups, and founders involved in these activities. The success of this promotion can be seen from the number of applicants and participants from the various EELISA institutions in the entrepreneurship activities that will be evaluated in the next chapter of this deliverable.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the EELISA InnoCORE Innovation & Entrepreneurship Webpage

For those who are already more advanced in their innovation and entrepreneurship journey, the webpage offers three different programs and events, gives a short description of them and also provides links to the respective event webpages from which the events can be joined. The EELISA InnoCORE innovation and entrepreneurship webpage is a very useful tool that should be continued in EELISA phase II. However, in contrast to the programs, courses, and events promoted on the webpage, the webpage itself is not an entrepreneurship activity that will be further evaluated in this deliverable.

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Fifthly, the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan proposed to transform the mapping of the EELISA landscape of startup support or at least those elements that are English-speaking and open to EELISA into an overview on the EELISA website to make our startup support resources more visible as well as better accessible and coordinated. This idea, without being an entrepreneurship activity itself, has been achieved in January 2024 with the launch of the following webpage: <https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/>. The webpage provides an overview of the innovation and entrepreneurship programs, courses, and events that are offered regularly and are open to EELISA. Additionally, it encourages visitors to join the "Entrepreneurship without borders" community on the EELISA Community Platform to get to know about additional activities that are offered irregularly. For those who are at the beginning of their entrepreneurship journey, the webpage offers five different programs, courses, and events, gives a short description of them and provides links to the respective event webpages from which the events can be joined.

Sixthly, we continued our discussions about connecting and sharing our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses by joint events and small thematic meetings also integrating key stakeholders from these institutions and services into the discussions not only to learn from each other, but also to systematically interconnect our resources and to develop additional offers for our potential and actual startups and founders. In that regard, we had several work package 7 meetings, visits of our partner incubators and startup support institutions (our startup consulting services, ZOLLHOF, JOSEPHS, Station F, D.School Paris, PSL Lab, etc.) and meetings with venture capital investors. The strongest and most tangible results of these meetings were the newly created EELISA entrepreneurship activities that will be evaluated in the next chapter of this deliverable: The EELISA Entrepreneurship School and EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event.

Seventhly, we have not only opened and shared existing offers of startup support among all members of our EELISA European University, but also filled some gaps and created attractive and highly demanded new joint offers. This was done by the activities proposed in the third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan.

3. The third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan outlined the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative for the third year of the EELISA InnoCORE project between June 2023 and May 2024. Our aim with this initiative was not only to open as many of the existing key startup support institutions, services, programs and courses listed in the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan by the means proposed in the second pillar, but also to fill the gaps in the EELISA landscape of startup support by organizing additional joint events for our startups and founders aiming to create new opportunities and added value for them. In particular, by opening our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems for startups from EELISA partners we wanted to offer our startups the additional opportunities that such a European ecosystem can offer and to increase the probability of their success on the European market. Therefore, we planned to organize activities that would provide them with new skills, knowledge, and access to networks from which they would benefit on their startup journey. These activities might have been boot camps, workshops, mentoring programs, demo days, and startup contests. What was important was that these activities would give our startups access to an advanced EELISA landscape of startup support where they would:

- profit from the startup support expertise and resources that can be provided by EELISA European University,
- get access to EELISA partners' innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems beyond their home institutions,
- get informed about how investors actually work in different national markets,
- become familiar with general basics like “product market fit”, “investor readiness”, “pitching” or “negotiation”,
- learn about the methods of design thinking,
- have the possibility to learn from each other and from more advanced startups,
- get the opportunity to collaborate on a European level and to build an international network already at an early stage,

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- get international feedback and the opportunity to further improve their business plans,
- and have the possibility and support (in the ideal case also the financial support of investors) to scale on a European level.

In the actual roll out phase of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan between June 2023 and May 2024, we succeeded not only in opening various entrepreneurship activities to all EELISA partners, but also in further enriching our EELISA landscape of startup support by creating two major EELISA entrepreneurship activities from scratch: One for very early stage startups and nascent founders, the EELISA Entrepreneurship School, and one for advanced startups, EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event. By having implemented this EELISA-wide startup initiative we can be confident to have leveraged the expertise and resources of EELISA European University to help our startups and founders transform their ideas into successful businesses that will contribute to the creation of a desirable future. The evaluation of our joint entrepreneurial activities in the following chapter will be exactly about these activities.

Now that we have a better idea of the EELISA entrepreneurship activities to be evaluated, a few comments about the evaluation itself may be in order. The description of deliverable 7.4 in the EELISA InnoCORE Grant Agreement simply states that the evaluation of joint entrepreneurial activities will include “a preliminary outcome evaluation”. The nature of the outcomes to be evaluated is further described in the corresponding EELISA InnoCORE task 7.2 where it is stated that “we will closely track the outcomes” of the EELISA entrepreneurship activities “and draw a preliminary evaluation of the success of the measures (e.g. number of events and consultations, start-ups generated, funding and venture capital acquired).” As can be seen from this exemplary list, the evaluation has to be specific to the kind of event (since it does not, for example, make sense to evaluate the amount of venture capital acquired in an event for very early-stage startups and nascent entrepreneurs like the EELISA Entrepreneurship School nor the number of startups generated in an event for advanced startups like EELISA Next Level). Thus, in the following chapter, we will list all EELISA entrepreneurship activities that took place in the roll out phase of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan between June 2023 and May 2024 and evaluate them either together, where it makes sense, or individually. For the entrepreneurship activities organized by the startup consulting services of EELISA partners that were opened to EELISA we will give some basic information about the activities and as far as possible provide the number of participants. This will be done in the first part of the next chapter. In the second part, we will evaluate the entrepreneurship activities that were newly created for EELISA. Since these activities were organized by EELISA InnoCORE WP7 and specifically created for EELISA, there is much more information about these activities that can be evaluated individually and also much higher participation from all EELISA partners in these activities.

3 Evaluation of EELISA entrepreneurship activities

This chapter provides an evaluation of the EELISA entrepreneurship activities during the roll out phase of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan from June 2023 to May 2024. The first

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part of the chapter evaluates the various entrepreneurship activities that were opened to EELISA and the second part of the chapter evaluates the entrepreneurship activities that were newly created for EELISA. Most notable among these activities and among our EELISA entrepreneurship activities in general are the EELISA Entrepreneurship School and EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event. It should be noted here that in addition to these activities, during the reporting period from June 2023 to May 2024, we also offered two EELISA Innovation Talks on topics related to entrepreneurship (EELISA Innovation Talk # 11 at PSL on “Deeptech Entrepreneurship & Innovation” and EELISA Innovation Talk # 12 at UPB on “Unleashing the potential: Navigating the Early Stage of Spinoff and Startup Business Development”) reported in D7.7, as well as the various EELISA innovation and co-creation activities reported in D7.3, which are also closely related to entrepreneurship as well.

3.1 Evaluation of entrepreneurship activities that were opened to EELISA

During the reporting period from June 2023 to May 2024, various entrepreneurship activities were opened to EELISA and offered via EELISA media channels for innovation to EELISA students, startups, researchers, innovators, and staff. The following will be an evaluation and an overview of these activities. **In total, we succeeded in opening 11 entrepreneurship activities at five different EELISA institutions to all EELISA partners. 8 of these 11 activities were on the level of nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge), 2 were on the level of incubation and acceleration (advanced and professional startup skills and knowledge) and 1 was on the level of acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge). These activities were attended by at least 1,281 participants (although for two of these activities no data about participant numbers is available). Furthermore, these activities were attended by at least 48 participants from EELISA institutions other than the one offering the activity (although for two of these activities no data about participant numbers from other EELISA institutions than the one offering the activity is available). Taking into account only the entrepreneurship activities for which the number of participants is available, the entrepreneurship activities opened to EELISA were attended on average by five participants from EELISA partners other than the institution offering the event.** The promotion of these activities among all EELISA partners seems to be crucial for a high number of participants from all institutions. The following is an overview of the entrepreneurship activities that were opened to all EELISA partners during the reporting period from June 2023 to May 2024.

3.1.1 “Actúaupm” offered by UPM

Name of the activity	Actúaupm
Short description of the activity	ACTÚAUPM, the UPM Entrepreneurship Program, has as its main objective the generation of innovative companies with high growth potential and supporting the entrepreneurial spirit. It develops its work around four pillars:

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	the business idea, the team, the resources that support the project, and the business model that the three previous concepts give rise to. ACTÚAUPM program services are: Follow-up from the initial phase to the establishment of the company; analysis of the feasibility of the project; ongoing advice; guidance in the writing of the business plan; training actions geared to the needs of the team; visibility for investors and support in the search for financing; and the actúaupm Business Creation Competition with already nineteen editions held.
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	Training
Target group	University entrepreneurs
Event webpage	www.upm.es/actuaupm https://eelisa.eu/events/join-the-competition-actuaupms-start-up-contest-is-now-open-for-eelisa-members/ https://eelisa.eu/events/join-the-third-phase-of-actua-upms-start-up-contest-now-open-for-eelisa-members/
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	See on the event webpages www.upm.es/actuaupm https://eelisa.eu/events/join-the-third-phase-of-actua-upms-start-up-contest-now-open-for-eelisa-members/
Application deadline	21 March 2023
Date of the activity	April – December 2023
Location of the activity	Online via Zoom
Number of participants	456
Number of participants from EELISA partners	441 from UPM, 9 from ITU, 3 from BME, 2 from FAU, 1 from SNS

Table 2: “Actúaupm” offered by UPM

3.1.2 “Starting Business Ideas @FAU” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	Starting Business Ideas @FAU
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Short description of the activity	<p>Welcome to the workshop series Starting Business Ideas @ FAU! Entrepreneur, intrapreneur, freelancer, project team, founding team, start-up?! – this platform is for you. We help you getting started with the Business Design process right away from your idea until the stage where you can start validating your idea. The series consists of six workshops which will take place virtually as Zoom events. Everyone from FAU, Existency, and EELISA can participate. The workshop series consists of several parts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part 0: Ideation Workshop • Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • Part 2: Business Model Workshop • Part 3: Prototyping – Done is better than perfect! • Part 4: Business Model World Café • Part 5: Financial Modeling Workshop • Part 6: 1-1 Coaching MeetUp <p>For further information, see https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/.</p>
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	<p>Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)</p>
Type of activity	<p>Workshop</p>
Target group	<p>Everybody from EELISA interested in starting business ideas</p>
Event webpage	<p>https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/</p> <p>https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/#1705050454815-70875429-17f4</p>
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	<p>You can take part in each workshop individually concerning your interest and state of development of your founding endeavor. Registration webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/#collapse_7</p>
Application deadline	<p>The workshops will take place via Zoom. Registration is possible until the last day before each workshop session. But please register as early as possible.</p>
Date of the activity	<p>The dates of the workshop sessions can be found on the event webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 27.04.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 0: Ideation Workshop • 09.05.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • 23.05.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 2: Business Model Workshop • 13.06.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 3: Prototyping • 27.06.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 4: Business Model World Café

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 04.07.2023, 16:00-19:00 (CEST): Part 5: Financial Modeling Workshop • 11.07.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 6: 1-1 Coaching Meetup
Location of the activity	See https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/
Number of participants	160
Number of participants from EELISA partners	(probably) 159 from FAU and 1 from another EELISA partner

Table 3: “Starting Business Ideas @FAU” offered by FAU

3.1.3 “Medical Valley Services for Startups” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	Medical Valley Services for Startups
Short description of the activity	<p>We offer customized services for all startup stages and beyond – from the first steps to business formation to the international market entry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Startup consulting: We have been consulting founders in the healthcare and medical technology sector since 2003. With our know-how and partner network we help you define your business plan. - Incubator & office space: Together with our incubators Medical Valley Center Erlangen and Medical Valley Center Forchheim we offer high-growth companies in the healthcare industry excellent office space in one of the economically strongest and scientifically most active healthcare clusters worldwide – the Medical Valley European Metropolitan Region Nuremberg. A total of almost 7,000 m² of flexible and representative office space is available. In the Medical Valley Centers in Erlangen and Forchheim, you will sit alongside with other startups and growth companies and have daily access to our Medical Valley team and service portfolio. - Access to healthcare-specific startup programs: In the last few years many startup programs have been established: bootcamps, hackathons, business plan competitions or accelerator programs. We help you identify the right ones for your respective business situation. - Venture capital: We support you in finding the right investors for your company – during all startup stages and beyond. We are connected to relevant healthcare investors, such as angel investors, VC funds, corporate VCs or equity crowdfunding providers. - Acquisition of funds: For you, we scout for the right funding programs at state, federal and EU level. Since 2010, we have raised more than 150 million € in funding for our partners.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to strategic partners: We are directly linked to partners in industry, research, healthcare and politics, so we can introduce you to potential business partners. - Venture building: If you are looking for suitable partners to bring your idea or startup to life, Medical Valley GmbH can co-found startups as a startup factory. This means, for example, if you are a doctor or researcher with ideas that are ready for commercialization, but you wish to remain a doctor or researcher, we can – in selected cases - , jointly found a startup. In the last three years we have actively participated in three medical technology startups and have taken on management duties. - Certification, approval, reimbursement: To successfully launch your medical device on the market, a precise and accurate planning of your regulatory strategy is indispensable. We will provide guidance to help you find the right person for the approval of your product. Moreover, we can also help you with your reimbursement strategy. We are affiliated with numerous public and private health insurance companies in Germany and offer unique medical, technical and health economic validation support with our dmac (Digital Medical Application Center). - Internationalization: Are you looking for a way to access international markets? We make sure that you don't have to go down this road alone by determining potential markets in advance and transparently highlighting relevant conditions. Market analysis, development of regulatory strategies and on-site visits help you to develop a comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges of the target country. If you are interested in entering the German market, we are also there to assist you. We can provide you with essential information about the German market and the healthcare system and work out the optimal project plan together with you. <p>You don't know where to start? Are you looking for impulses, inspiration, answers or the right questions? If you don't know what you need to bring your startup forward or if you are interested in topics that are not listed here, please, feel free to contact us.</p>
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Incubation (advanced startup skills and knowledge) and acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	Various services startups in the health sector
Target group	Startups from the health sector
Event webpage	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/ https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/#1705050460442-a30fb3f3-c53c

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Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	For contact see https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/
Application deadline	Application is always possible.
Date of the activity	Ongoing activities
Location of the activity	For further information see https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/
Number of participants	No data available
Number of participants from EELISA partners	No data available

Table 4: “Medical Valley Services for Startups” offered by FAU

3.1.4 “Change makers: Shaping the future” offered by UPM

Name of the activity	Change makers: Shaping the future
Short description of the activity	Join the course “Change makers: Shaping the future” and learn to succeed in the rapidly evolving online world. In this practical course, you will discover tools and methodologies for innovators, based on new developments and opportunities presented in this new era. Participants will work in teams and develop a real project with guidance from experienced entrepreneurs and academics. It will be held online through the platform Zoom from November 2nd to November 30th. The schedule for the fall semester is every Tuesday and Thursday from 2:30 p.m. to 5:30 p.m. and 2:30 p.m. to 5 p.m. CET respectively. Students are requested to interact during the lessons, work in teams, complete tasks, read the references assigned, and provide results for the assignments. All materials will be available online upon the start. In addition to class, the students will be encouraged to participate in innovation/leadership/entrepreneurship-related events that will be announced during the class. This is an entrepreneurship activity of the EELISA innoCORE project.
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	Entrepreneurship course
Target group	Students
Event webpage	https://eelisa.eu/events/change-makers-shaping-the-future-training-session-i-into-the-pitch/

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Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://educadn.typeform.com/to/SlqUNzHJ?typeform-source=eelisa.eu
Application deadline	1 November 2023
Date of the activity	2 – 30 November 2023, Tuesday 2:30-5:30 pm and Thursday 2:30-5:00 pm (CET)
Location of the activity	Online via Zoom
Number of participants	304 participants
Number of participants from EELISA partners	81 from UPM, 4 from ITU, 4 from UPB, 2 from FAU, 2 from SNS, 1 from BME

Table 5: “Change makers: Shaping the future” offered by UPM

3.1.5 “Starting Business Ideas @FAU” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	Starting Business Ideas @FAU
Short description of the activity	<p>Welcome to the workshop series Starting Business Ideas @ FAU! Entrepreneur, intrapreneur, freelancer, project team, founding team, start-up?! – this platform is for you. Kick off your startup journey with our workshop series that covers everything from defining a value proposition and business model, prototyping, financial modeling, pitching, feedback and 1-on-1 consulting. The series consists of eight workshops delivered virtually as Zoom events. Everyone from FAU, Existency, and EELISA can participate. The workshop series consists of several parts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part 0: Ideation Workshop • Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • Part 2: Business Model Workshop • Part 3: Prototyping – Done is better than perfect! • Part 4: Pitching Best Practices • Part 5: Business Model World Café • Part 6: Financial Modeling Workshop • Part 7: 1-1 Coaching MeetUp <p>For further information, see https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/.</p>
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)

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Type of activity	Workshop
Target group	Everybody from EELISA interested in starting business ideas
Event webpage	https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/ https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/#1705050454815-70875429-17f4
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	You can take part in each workshop individually concerning your interest and state of development of your founding endeavor. Registration webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/#collapse_8
Application deadline	The workshops will take place via Zoom. Registration is possible until the last day before each workshop session. But please register as early as possible.
Date of the activity	The dates of the workshop sessions can be found on the event webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 07.11.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 0: Ideation Workshop • 14.11.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • 28.11.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 2: Business Model Workshop • 12.12.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 3: Prototyping • 09.01.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 4: Pitching Best Practices • 16.01.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET) Part 5: Business Model World Café • 23.01.2024, 16:00-19:00 (CET): Part 6: Financial Modeling Workshop • 25.01.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 7: 1-1 Coaching Meetup
Location of the activity	See https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/
Number of participants	150
Number of participants from EELISA partners	(probably) 150 from FAU

Table 6: “Starting Business Ideas @FAU” offered by FAU

3.1.6 “Clean Cities Spain ClimAccelerator” offered by UPM

Name of the activity	Clean Cities Spain ClimAccelerator
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Short description of the activity	<p>Clean Cities Spain ClimAccelerator is an accelerator that, with the support of EIT Climate-KIC, aims to support European startups focused on the fight against climate change in cities. Cities face an enormous challenge: They must become more resilient and healthy places to live while reaching net-zero-emissions in just a few short years. The Clean Cities ClimAccelerator is an accelerator program, launched in 2020 with the support of EIT Climate-KIC, with a strong focus on the impact of climate change in urban areas and the commercialization of clean technology (cleantech). It targets start-ups that are developing solutions with special focus on transforming city systems to become climate neutral—from mobility to waste, energy to health, and the built environment. The programme is looking for start-ups with the capability to contribute to systemic change in cities, and that can work in multi-stakeholder ecosystems.</p> <p>The call is open until October 30, 2023 (until 11:59 p.m.). And these are the benefits that the selected startups will enjoy in this initiative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Access to a global network of investors, corporations and public institutions. – Training sessions with international speakers specialized in the area of business and sustainability. – Access to the EIT Climate-KIC ecosystem to boost your startup. – Visibility, marketing and individualized communication actions. – And much more!
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	<p>Acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)</p>
Type of activity	<p>Accelerator program</p>
Target group	<p>European startups focused on the fight against climate change in cities</p>
Event webpage	<p>https://eelisa.eu/events/clean-cities-spain-climaccelerator/</p>
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	<p>https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSc0iEQvLcPX95192Wv7f3RDnObli6rVjCNKFnP0nohPufMTvg/closedform</p> <p>In case you have any doubt, do not hesitate to contact the program's managers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Elisa Navarro: elisa.navarro@upm.es – Ana Horta: ana.horta@upm.es
Application deadline	<p>30 October 2023</p>
Date of the activity	<p>9 November 2023 – 7 March 2024</p>
Location of the activity	<p>Most of the activities will be online or hybrid. We reserve the right to carry out the activities in person at UPM.</p>

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Number of participants	50
Number of participants from EELISA partners	6 from UPM

Table 7: “Clean Cities Spain ClimAccelerator” offered by UPM

3.1.7 “EU Funding Tools for Entrepreneurs” offered by UPM

Name of the activity	EU Funding Tools for Entrepreneurs
Short description of the activity	<p>Do you know anything about EU Funding tools? Learn how to use them on this informative session for entrepreneurs</p> <p>This informative session will delve into the world of European Union (EU) funding programs and opportunities tailored specifically for startups. Attendees will gain valuable insights into the various funding avenues, grants, and resources available within the EU ecosystem to fuel their entrepreneurial ventures. The session will cover essential topics such as grant application processes, eligibility criteria, and key strategies for securing EU funding. Whether you’re a budding entrepreneur or an established startup, this session will provide you with the knowledge and tools needed to navigate the EU funding tollways to drive your startup toward success. This is an entrepreneurship activity of the EELISA innoCORE project.</p> <p>Speaker: Evelio Jiménez</p> <p>Evelio Jimeno Ruiz is an Expert in R&D funding programs such as Horizon Europe and the Spanish Next generation. He graduated in Industrial Engineering in 2006, Diploma of Advanced Studies in project Management, and having studied part of his studies in Ireland. He then worked as an engineer, before moving into sales and consulting. In 2016, he founded EJ Innovation, a consultancy firm that helps startups and deep tech companies secure funding from European and Spanish grants. Evelio is passionate about technology, finances, and innovation. He is also a strong leader and team player, multidisciplinary profile, extroverted, entrepreneurial, organized and demanding. He is always looking for new challenges and opportunities to help others.</p>
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Incubation (advanced startup skills and knowledge) and acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	Info session
Target group	Startups and entrepreneurs
Event webpage	https://eelisa.eu/events/do-you-know-anything-about-eu-funding-tools-learn-how-to-use-them-on-this-informative-session-for-entrepreneurs/

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Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdSFtK0TarexqjJ-p1grJjkdhSbkfQVukJEB4RIdB1hhxW_DQ/viewform Contact e-mail address: creacion.empresas@upm.es
Application deadline	None
Date of the activity	16 November 2023 from 10:00 to 11:30 (CET)
Location of the activity	Online via Zoom
Number of participants	28 participants
Number of participants from EELISA partners	13 from UPM, 3 from ITU, 3 from SNS, 2 from UPB, and 1 from BME

Table 8: “EU Funding Tools for Entrepreneurs” offered by UPM

3.1.8 “Une Nuit pour Entreprendre” offered by ENPC

Name of the activity	Une Nuit pour Entreprendre
Short description of the activity	<p>L'École des Ponts ParisTech lance la 9ème édition d'Une Nuit Pour Entreprendre ! Cet événement d'initiation à la création d'entreprise encourage les élèves à développer leur créativité et leur esprit d'entreprendre. En travaillant par petits groupes, les étudiants ont une nuit pour élaborer un projet innovant. Ces projets sont soumis au petit matin à un jury composé de membres de l'École et d'entrepreneurs. Après avoir assisté au témoignage d'un entrepreneur, les étudiants participent à l'atelier de lancement des projets, préambule d'un travail collaboratif sous la tutelle de professionnels expérimentés. Les projets sont ensuite présentés entre 7h et 9h30 à un jury composé de la direction de l'École, d'anciens élèves devenus entrepreneurs et de professionnels reconnus qui évaluent leur pertinence et leur viabilité. Des récompenses seront remises aux meilleures équipes par la Fondation des Ponts et et la Fondation Singular Planet, ainsi que par Vinci et L'Oréal, entreprises partenaires.</p> <p>Ce concours s'adresse aux élèves de l'École mais également issus d'autres établissements de l'enseignement supérieur d'Ile-de-France et de l'université européenne EELISA, qu'ils soient portés vers la création d'entreprise, qu'ils aient déjà un projet en tête ou qu'ils soient dans une démarche de découverte.</p>
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)

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Type of activity	Hackathon
Target group	Students
Event webpage	https://ecoledespoints.fr/9eme-edition-dune-nuit-pour-entreprendre
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.eventbrite.fr/e/inscription-une-nuit-pour-entreprendre-2023-709424837787
Application deadline	23 November 2023
Date of the activity	7 December 2023
Location of the activity	ENPC
Number of participants	75 students
Number of participants from EELISA partners	48 from ENPC, 2 from FAU

Table 9: “Une Nuit Pour Entreprendre” offered by ENPC

3.1.9 “Technology transfer in nanotechnologies: IP protection, spin-offs” offered by SNS

Name of the activity	Technology transfer in nanotechnologies: IP protection, spin-offs
Short description of the activity	The course will cover the basis of innovation exploitation at universities and the path of growth and maturation of a spin-offs/start ups. Teachers from universities of the European University EELISA, which the school is part of, will also be involved. In addition, are awaited contributions from leading companies in the field of innovation: Deloitte, Hoffmann Eitler; while ARTES 4.0 will be present as Italian innovation ecosystem.
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To provide students with the basic knowledge on University third mission, with a specific emphasis on the opportunities at SNS. - To deepen the issues of technology and knowledge transfer, innovation management, patent and IP management, starting a spin-off, tools for enterprise acceleration and support.

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Target group	PhD students
Event webpage	https://www.sns.it/en/avviso/course-technology-transfer-nanotechnologies-ip-protection-spin-offs-prof-guerrini
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	andrea.guerrini@sns.it
Application deadline	November 2023
Date of the activity	January-April
Location of the activity	Aula Mancini at SNS
Number of participants	13
Number of participants from EELISA partners	13 from SNS

Table 10: “Technology transfer in nanotechnologies: IP protection, spin-offs” offered by SNS

3.1.10 “High-tech Entrepreneurship” offered by SSSA

Name of the activity	High-tech Entrepreneurship
Short description of the activity	<p>This 20-hours course is designed to introduce participants, PhD and undergraduate students from different disciplines (STEM, but also Social Sciences and Humanities) and also young researchers and post-docs, to the basic knowledge and competences about high-tech entrepreneurship. More precisely, the course will provide participants with the basic understanding of the role, analytics and process of business planning that leads to the creation of new innovative business ventures, especially regarding those which are generated within an academic environment, on the basis of public research. They will learn and gain direct experience about patents, university-industry collaborations, contract research, starting a new company, marketing high-tech inventions, etc. The objective is to bring participants to have their business model and business plan ready at the end of the course. Participants will also have the opportunity of setting up real proposals for start-ups which they will be able to use for start-up competitions such as Start Cup Toscana or other possible calls launched by Sant’Anna and other universities.</p> <p>The course is designed mainly – but not only – for participants from universities which are part of the JoTTO initiative (i.e. Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Scuola Normale Superiore, IMT Lucca, IUSS Pavia, GSSI L’Aquila, SISSA Trieste). Students from other universities and from EELISA Network can also apply. The course has been designed both for those who</p>

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	are planning to set up an innovative and/or high-tech start-up and for those who might benefit from the course's contents in an existing company, in their professional activities or in a research context. The course is organized in collaboration with the EELISA project and Start Cup Toscana.
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	Course
Target group	PhD and undergraduate students from different disciplines (STEM, but also Social Sciences and Humanities) and also young researchers and post-docs
Event webpage	https://eelisa.eu/events/learn-the-role-analytics-and-process-of-business-planning-through-high-tech-entrepreneurship/
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Register by sending an e mail to a.piccaluga@santannapisa.it and Giovanni.Tolin@santannapisa.it
Application deadline	none
Date of the activity	From March 4th 2024 at 3:00 p.m. (CEST) to May 17th 2024, at 6:00 p.m. (CEST)
Location of the activity	Onsite at Aula magna storica, piazza martiri della liberta 33, Pisa and online: https://santannapisa.webex.com/meet/andrea.piccaluga
Number of participants	45
Number of participants from EELISA partners	37 from SSSA, 4 from SNS, 3 from ITU, 1 from UPB

Table 11: “High-tech Entrepreneurship” offered by SSSA

3.1.11 “Starting Business Ideas @FAU” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	Starting Business Ideas @FAU
Short description of the activity	Welcome to the workshop series Starting Business Ideas @ FAU! Entrepreneur, intrapreneur, freelancer, project team, founding team, start-up?! – this platform is for you. Kick off your startup journey with our workshop series that covers everything from defining a value proposition and business model, prototyping, financial modeling, pitching, feedback and 1-on-1 consulting. The series consists of eight workshops delivered virtually as

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	<p>Zoom events. Everyone from FAU, Existency, and EELISA can participate. The workshop series consists of several parts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part 0: Ideation Workshop • Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • Part 2: Business Model Workshop • Part 3: Prototyping – Done is better than perfect! • Part 4: Pitching Best Practices • Part 5: SBI Pitch • Part 6: Revenue Models & Financial Modeling Workshop • Part 7: 1-1 Coaching MeetUp <p>For further information, see https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/.</p>
Skill level of the activity (nucleation, incubation, or acceleration)	Nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)
Type of activity	Workshop
Target group	Everybody from EELISA interested in starting business ideas
Event webpage	<p>https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/</p> <p>https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/#1705050454815-70875429-17f4</p>
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	<p>You can take part in each workshop individually concerning your interest and state of development of your founding endeavor. Registration webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/#collapse_8</p>
Application deadline	The workshops will take place via Zoom. Registration is possible until the last day before each workshop session. But please register as early as possible.
Date of the activity	<p>The dates of the workshop sessions can be found on the event webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25.04.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 0: Ideation Workshop • 07.05.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • 14.05.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 2: Business Model Workshop • 04.06.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 3: Prototyping • 18.06.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 4: Pitching Best Practices • 02.07.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET) Part 5: SBI Pitch • 09.07.2024, 16:00-19:00 (CET): Part 6: Revenue Models & Financial Modeling Workshop • 16.07.2024, 16:00-18:00 (CET): Part 7: 1-1 Coaching Meetup

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Location of the activity	See https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/
Number of participants	No data available (The workshop series has not yet been completed at the time of submission of this deliverable.)
Number of participants from EELISA partners	No data available (The workshop series has not yet been completed at the time of submission of this deliverable.)

Table 12: “Starting Business Ideas @FAU” offered by FAU

3.2 Evaluation of new EELISA entrepreneurship activities

During the implementation phase of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan from June 2023 to May 2024, we not only opened entrepreneurship activities to all EELISA partners, but also created new EELISA entrepreneurship activities from scratch. These new EELISA entrepreneurship activities have been designed to complement our EELISA landscape of startup support in two key strategic areas: The nucleation of new startups and the acceleration of advanced startups. To nucleate new startups, we have set up the first edition of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School. The EELISA Entrepreneurship School has been designed to help potential founders from all EELISA partners learn how to develop a first business idea into a viable business model and the entrepreneurship toolkit necessary to launch their own startup. The goal was to disseminate an entrepreneurial mindset and skills among EELISA students and to finally increase the number and quality of startups created in EELISA. Additionally, we also aimed to accelerated already existing advanced startups by giving them access to our first-class European network of incubators and investors which comprises among others Station F in Paris, the largest startup campus in the world, or ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator, the fastest growing tech incubator in Germany with their respective mentors, highly successful startups, and networks of investors. The event that we created for this purpose was “EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event” at ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator. The following will be an evaluation including a preliminary outcome evaluation of these joint entrepreneurship activities that were newly created for EELISA and promoted via EELISA media channels for innovation among EELISA students, staff, startups, researchers, innovators, venture capital investors, business angels, and other external stakeholders during the reporting period from June 2023 to May 2024.

3.2.1 Evaluation of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School offered by FAU

Name of the activity	EELISA Entrepreneurship School
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<p>Event banner</p>	<p>The banner features the FAU and EELISA logos at the top. The main title 'EELISA ENTREPRENEURSHIP SCHOOL' is in large white letters. Below it, the dates 'FROM 16 TO 20 OCTOBER 2023' and location 'FAU, RESEARCH CAMPUS WAISCHENFELD' are listed. A gold glitter band contains the text 'GET THE EELISA ENTREPRENEURSHIP EXPERIENCE FOR FURTHER INFORMATION, SEE EELISA.FAU.DE/INNOVATORS_ENTREPRENEURS/EES/'. At the bottom, a small European Union flag and funding text are visible.</p>
<p>Short description of the activity</p>	<p>Get the EELISA Entrepreneurship Experience! FAU invites innovative talents from all EELISA partners to the first EELISA Entrepreneurship School at the Research Campus Waischenfeld in Germany from 16th to 20th October 2023. The EELISA Entrepreneurship School is a one-week program for EELISA students and staff from all disciplines who can apply either as an ideator with a first business idea or as a co-creator motivated to join another participant's business idea during the program. All participants must be highly motivated to learn about developing a first business idea into a viable business model and the entrepreneurship toolkit necessary for founding their own startup. After their time together in Waischenfeld, all 25 participants will have taken the first steps on their entrepreneurship journey and will be in a much better position to start their own business.</p> <p>Programme</p> <p>At the EELISA Entrepreneurship School you will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - form interdisciplinary teams with potential founders from all over Europe and work together to develop your business ideas,

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - meet experts and startups from FAU's excellent innovation ecosystem, - learn about business model generation, value proposition design, prototyping, validation and much more, - develop your ideas with Lego Serious Play, - produce a video in a storytelling workshop, - be prepared to finally pitch your business model, - and receive EELISA credentials upon successful completion of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School. <p>For further information, see the event webpage: https://www.eelisa.fau.de/innovators_entrepreneurs/ees/ https://eelisa.eu/events/do-you-want-to-upskill-your-talent-join-the-first-eelisa-entrepreneurship-school/</p>
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	Fraunhofer-Forschungscampus, Fraunhofer-Platz 1, 91344 Waischenfeld, Germany
Type of activity	One-week entrepreneurship seasonal school
Target group	Innovative talents from all EELISA partners
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.eelisa.fau.de/innovators_entrepreneurs/ees/#collapse_2
Application deadline	15 September 2023
Dates of the activity	16-20 October 2023
Number of participants	26 students
Number of participants from EELISA partners	14 from FAU, 3 from BME, 2 from PSL, 2 from ENPC, 2 from UPM, 2 from ITU, 1 from SSSA
Evaluation	<p>The EELISA Entrepreneurship School has been a great success and has received excellent feedback from its participants, who have been equipped with the necessary tools to create their own startups. In fact, several of the participants went on to found their own startups after their positive experience at the EELISA Entrepreneurship School. But what made the program so attractive and successful?</p> <p>We will start our evaluation from the beginning: We received a total of 165 applications most of which came from FAU (99) and ITU (33), followed by BME (13), SSSA (7), PSL (5), ENPC (4), and UPM (4). No applications were received from SNS and UPB. From this large number of applications, we selected the top candidates who also had to get funding for travel support</p>

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	<p>from their respective home institutions or be willing to cover the travel costs themselves (subsistence costs were covered by the program). Finally, we invited 26 innovative talents from 7 EELISA partners who applied either as ideators or co-creators to participate in the first edition of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School from 16 to 20 October 2024 at the Fraunhofer Research Campus in Waischenfeld, Germany. The location was well chosen, since there were no distractions in the small village and the participants could focus on the program and the work on their business ideas and projects.</p> <p>On the first day of the program, we met in Nuremberg and went together by bus to Waischenfeld. We started the program with a “Welcome & Introduction”, a first “Get to know each other”, and a team building session. In the evening we had a panel discussion with several startups who shared their experience and were open to the questions of the participants of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School.</p> <p>For the second day, we had invited two experts from the FAU innovation ecosystem to lead four sessions on the topics “Introduction to Business Design” and “Customer Centric Innovation”. In the afternoon, the students who had successfully applied to the program as ideators were given some time to prepare their business idea pitches, which were then presented in a pitch session with the goal of forming teams around the most promising business ideas, as voted on by all participants. In this way, the top five business ideas were selected, and teams of four to six members were formed from the 21 co-creators around the top five ideators of their choice. These five teams spent the remainder of the program working together to further develop their respective business ideas.</p> <p>The next morning started with two Lego Serious Play sessions in which the teams were working on the clarification and further development of their business ideas and the team members’ respective role in their team. In the afternoon, the teams learned about business model generation including value proposition design and worked intensely on their business model canvases. Afterwards, they were introduced to prototyping and producing short videos about their value proposition, which they worked on throughout the evening and in some cases late into the night.</p> <p>These short value proposition videos were shown the next morning and feedback was provided. Afterwards, another highlight were two pitch training sessions and a session on entrepreneurial thinking given by an expert from ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator. In the afternoon the teams had some time to prepare their pitches for the final pitch competition the next morning. In the evening, the participants of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School had the opportunity to learn from another successful startup founder who shared his experiences in an inspiring presentation followed by a Q&A session.</p> <p>On the last day of the program, the five teams finally pitched their business models and great progress could be seen compared to the first day of the program. The best three teams received the EELISA Entrepreneurship School Best Pitch Awards from a jury. Finally, the teams learned about “Next Steps & Early-stage Financing” from the Head of FAU’s startup consulting services before the bus brought all participants back to Nuremberg.</p>
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	<p>The EELISA Entrepreneurship School received excellent evaluations from its participants (17 out of 26 filled out the evaluation form): The question how they liked the EELISA Entrepreneurship School in general was answered by all participants with an average score of 3,94 on a scale from 1 (not at all) to 4 (it was great). The same score was received for the location. The average score for all sessions in response to the question “For your entrepreneurship learning experience at the EELISA Entrepreneurship School, the following session was important:” was 3,6 on a scale from 1 (totally disagree) to 4 (totally agree). The highest score was 3,82 for the two sessions on business model generation including value proposition design and the lowest, but still good to very good score was 3,41 for the video stage. The lowest, but still good scores were received for the panel discussion with the startups (3,24) and the individual startup talk (3,1). The overall excellent feedback is also reflected in the following examples of feedback that we received anonymously in our evaluation from the participants of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “In my opinion, it was one of the greatest experiences I had and I would definitely participate again and learn more new things from different topics. Thank you!” - “It was amazing! We were able to follow the schedule and there was enough time to work on everything.” - “First of all, the fact that everything was based on a specific plan was great. The event program that was prepared was followed quite well. Everything was very organized and well thought out to the smallest detail. I would like to extend my infinite thanks to our instructors Melanie and David who organized and conducted the event.” - “I appreciated the diverse range of topics covered at the EELISA Entrepreneurship School, and the hands-on approach to learning was particularly beneficial. The networking sessions, where students could interact with successful entrepreneurs and industry professionals, were invaluable. These elements, along with the practical case studies and interactive workshops, should definitely be retained in future iterations of the program.” - “I really enjoy this week in the entrepreneurship school. All the participants were really cool and it's definitely a great opportunity for people who don't know much about the topic to have an awesome first approach.” - “I liked the parts where we had to get active ourselves. Like producing the video or preparing the pitch.” - “It was really great and fun. I would probably just make it longer.” - “Thank you for this opportunity. I hope this programme gains more traction so that many more may benefit” - “It was an absolutely amazing time for me - thank you!” <p>Furthermore, we received feedback from students with their full names as testimonials that can be published. Here are some examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The EELISA Entrepreneurship School was a great experience. In one week, I met amazing people and perspectives from all over the world. We worked together intensively, but with a lot of fun. It was a great self-development journey!” (Yan Cruz, student from BME)
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "It was one of the best experiences of my life, very enriching. I learned a lot and enjoyed both the program and meeting so many people of different nationalities. Now, I feel more encouraged than ever to become an entrepreneur." (Javier Armas, student from FAU) - "This week at EELISA Entrepreneurship School was really enriching. The best way to connect with other entrepreneurs and students and evolve from a business idea to a professional business plan and pitch." (Margaux Lamy, student from PSL) - "It's a great opportunity to develop your idea or work on another idea. You get a lot of great input, but you also have enough free time to really get to know the other participants. I highly recommend it!" (Laura Zeltner, student from FAU) - "I had a very productive 5 days at the EELISA Entrepreneurship School organized by EELISA at FAU. I feel fortunate to have had the opportunity to improve myself here. Thank you :)" (Selva Dilek, student from ITU) - "I had a very amazing experience in the EELISA Entrepreneurship School that took place at FAU. The whole curriculum truly transformed my entrepreneurship journey. Practical activities, knowledge and networking I gained here are invaluable and I was able to deep dive into this field. Besides this, I had an opportunity to explore the place around and travel." (Gunel Bashirzade, student from BME) <p>About half a year after the EELISA Entrepreneurship School we know of at least four startups that were founded by participants of the program. We are convinced that the EELISA Entrepreneurship School has been a valuable complement to our EELISA landscape of startup support and it should be definitely continued in the future. We have experienced a very high demand for the program, that could be easily increased so that with additional resources even two EELISA Entrepreneurship Schools per year could be organized to meet the demand for such highly attractive European entrepreneurship programs. The one-week entrepreneurship training program was made possible through the funding of the EELISA InnoCORE project.</p>
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Pictures from the event

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Table 13: Evaluation of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School offered by FAU

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3.2.2 Evaluation of “EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event
Event banner	
Short description of the activity	<p>EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event</p> <p>If you believe your startup is among the top innovators within EELISA European University and you seek to secure seed or Series A funding, then you should definitely apply for “EELISA Next Level”, which will take place at ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator in Nuremberg, Germany, on 22 and 23 March 2024. EELISA Next Level is designed to be your seed and Series A funding booster, offering you both: pitch competition and networking event. Our network comprises top European incubators such as Station F in Paris, the largest startup campus in the world, or ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator, the fastest growing tech incubator in Germany (see the full list below) with their respective mentors, highly successful startups, and networks of investors.</p> <p>Benefits</p> <p>EELISA Next Level will not only give you the opportunity to pitch in front of investors, receive valuable feedback, and win the EELISA Next Level Startup Awards, but you will also participate in an exciting program that will give you the opportunity to expand your network, meet investors, learn from more experienced Series B and C startups, and help you to secure your seed or Series A funding to take your startup to the next level.</p> <p>Eligibility</p> <p>EELISA Next Level is open to all digital, tech, and deep tech startups (and spinoffs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - who have already mastered the pre-seed phase of their entrepreneurship journey and are now seeking seed or Series A funding (approximately 500k – 5 million €)

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - from all EELISA institutions including startups founded by at least one alumnus or alumna of an EELISA institution and startups from the following incubators connected to EELISA institutions: actúaupm (UPM), BME U[S]3 (BME), Chimie Paris Innov (PSL), Incubateur Descartes (ENPC), Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL), Innovation Labs (UPB), ITU Cekirdek (ITU), ITU Ginova (ITU), PC Up (PSL), Polo Tecnologico (SNS), Station F (ENPC), and ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU). <p>Our Jury of Investors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ariane Coletta, Investment Manager, Müller-Medien (Nürnberg) - Dr. Michael Hoeck, Venture Partner, Earlybird Venture Capital (Munich) - Julia Lang, Investment Professional, Tengelmann Ventures (Munich) - Katja Ruhnke, CEO and Angel Investor, CK-Venture Capital (Munich) - Eva-Juliane Stark, General Legal Counsel, Cavalry (Berlin) - Konstantin Urban, Founding Partner, G-Fund (Munich) <p>For further information and the agenda for both days of the event, see the event webpage https://www.eelisa.fau.de/eelisa-next-level/. See also https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-next-level-your-seed-and-series-a-funding-booster-event/.</p>
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator, Zollhof 7, 90443 Nuremberg, Germany
Type of activity	Startup contest (investor pitch competition), networking event, and expert talks (with Q&A sessions)
Target group	Advanced digital, tech, and deep tech startups from alle EELISA partners looking for seed and Series A funding, investors, business angels, startup consulting services, researchers and innovators, and everybody interested in the finalist startups, meeting investors and business angels, and seed and Series A funding topics
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Application webpage for the startups who wanted to participate in EELISA Next Level: https://www.eelisa.fau.de/eelisa-next-level-application/ Visitor registration webpage: https://www.eelisa.fau.de/eelisa-next-level-visitor-registration/
Application deadline	31 January 2024 for the startups who wanted to apply as finalists in EELISA Next Level and 19 March 2024 for the visitor registration
Dates of the activity	22 and 23 March 2024
Number of participants	About 120 (31 finalist startup participants, 6 members of the jury of investors, about 83 visitors)

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Number of participants from EELISA partners	34 from FAU, 10 from ITU, 8 from UPM, 3 from SNS, 3 from SSSA, 3 from BME, 2 from UPB, 1 from PSL, and 1 from ENPC (and about 55 external visitors about 25 of which were investors or business angels)
Finalist Startups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acalta (health startup from FAU): Acalta provides a care management platform to streamline the medical care journey for patients and healthcare providers using digital standardized clinical pathways. The solution optimizes clinical resource development, patient engagement and collaboration across the care team. For further information, see https://en.acalta.de/. - DriveByCloud (mobility startup from BME): Services exploiting Real-Time Digital Twin and infrastructure sensors. For further information, see https://drivebycloud.com/. - EyeCheckup (health startup from ITU Cekirdek (ITU)): Non-invasive diagnosis of eye, heart, and kidney diseases using AI. For further information, see https://www.eye-checkup.com/. - F-50 (health startup from ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)): F-50 offers online support for people suffering from eating disorders to help them get their everyday life back. For further information, see https://f-50.app/. - Hergele Mobility (mobility startup from ITU): At Hergele Mobility, we're redefining logistics with Wamo, our innovative micro-mobility solution. Agile, efficient, and user-friendly, Wamo is transforming warehouse operations and beyond. For further information, see https://www.hergele.co/. - Hydrolyca Energy Systems SL (greentech startup from UPM): Hydrolyca has developed a breakthrough technology for green hydrogen generation that bypasses conventional electrolysis. It is based on thermochemical reactions and uses heat as the primary energy source, such as solar power or waste heat from industry. (There is no website available.) - Hyperever (robotics startup from ITU): Hyperever Proteo, revolutionizing industrial inspection and construction tracking! For further information, see https://hyperever.com/. - INTA (health startup from SNS): INTA, a deep-tech startup from Italy, specializes in portable diagnostic devices for rapid blood-based brain trauma diagnosis. Its flagship product, NanoAnalyzer, offers a unique blend of AI-driven analytics and portability, tapping into a potential €900M TBI diagnosis market. For further information, see https://www.intasystems.net/. - Motorskins (hardware startup from ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)): Empowering objects with life at MotorSkins: Our soft-robotic materials add digital, movement, and interactive capabilities to everyday items, making them smart! We redefine healthcare, automotive, VR, and more with innovative interactive technology. For further information, see https://motorskins.com/. - Olivia (AI startup from SSSA): Olivia, a leader in restaurant data analysis, integrates AI and territorial data to optimize management, customer forecasts, procurement, and staffing. We identify culinary trends and business opportunities. The key to informed and strategic culinary success. For further information, see https://www.olivia-software.com/.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PCB Arts (hardware startup from ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)): Industrial machine vision is a key technology to make European manufacturing compatible again. We drive the integration of intelligent embedded systems, pioneering industry innovation with ease! For further information, see https://www.pcb-arts.com/de/. - Rayscape (health startup from Innovation Labs (UPB)): Rayscape is assisting radiologists in analysing medical images faster and more precise, with the help of an AI solution validated by 100+ hospitals throughout Europe. For further information, see https://rayscape.ai/. - Syntonym (AI startup from ITU): Generative AI for Privacy - anonymizing faces recorded by smart device cameras, ensuring data compliance, security, ethical use and personal privacy protection. For further information, see https://www.syntonym.com/. - Thermophoton (green tech startup from UPM): Thermophoton innovates with a latent heat thermal battery, providing electricity and heat through thermophotovoltaic tech. Exploiting VRE curtailment enables charging at remarkably low electric prices. For further information, see http://thermophoton.com/our-story.php. - traplinked (hardware startup from ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)): traplinked automates pest control through sensor-controlled trap systems. For further information, see https://www.traplinked.com/.
<p>Evaluation</p>	<p>“EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event” was designed to complement our EELISA landscape of startup support with an event for advanced digital, tech, and deep-tech startups from all EELISA partner institutions seeking seed or Series A funding between 500,000 € and 5,000,000 €. At the beginning, we neither knew if our event would attract enough high-quality startups nor if our event would also attract investors. But fortunately, it turned out that on both fronts our expectations were by far exceeded and the event with about 120 participants was a great success that we hope to institutionalize in a yearly EELISA Next Level event in EELISA phase II under WP10.</p> <p>The Call for EELISA Next Level was launched in January 2024, with the deadline for applications being January 31, 2024. We received 35 applications, of which the pre-selection jury selected the top 15 startups according to the evaluation criteria that were announced in the call as finalists for EELISA Next Level (cf. Annex I of this deliverable). In parallel, we were looking for investors, which was not easy in the beginning because it was the first event of its kind in our European University and the investors did not know exactly which startups to expect. It was mainly through ZOLLHOF’s network of investors that we could approach and find six great EELISA Next Level jury members and also attract about 25 investors and business angels to attend the event and even more who contacted the finalist startups before and after the event. Without any time overlap with other major European startup competitions we could have attracted even more investors to participate in the event. The great interest in the event from mainly German investors came as a very positive surprise. Additionally, there were also some investors involved from France, Italy, and Spain.</p> <p>The first day of the event was open to the public and was designed to be an investor pitch competition as well as a networking event. The 15 EELISA Next Level finalist startups each had three minutes for their investor pitch and</p>

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seven minutes for a subsequent Q&A with the jury of investors who judged the startups according to the evaluation criteria that were already announced in the call. Finally, the three startups who got the highest scores from the jury were awarded the EELISA Next Level Startup Awards: The first place was awarded to Syntonym (from ITU), the second place was awarded to Olivia (from SSSA), and the third place was awarded to Rayscape (from UPB). During the coffee breaks and the EELISA Next Level networking dinner, the finalist startups and the investors had many opportunities to get to know each other, exchange contact information, and talk about possible investments. The feedback that we received from the startups, the investors, and the audience was just great.

The second day of the event was designed for all finalist startups and all those interested in seed and Series A funding topics. As speakers, we had invited the senior investment manager at ZOLLHOF, a seasoned VC investor, and two startup founders who were successful in raising seed and Series A funding. All speakers shared their experiences, gave valuable information and advice, and were open to questions from the audience mainly composed of the finalist startups and some other startups and investors (about 50 participants in total). The second day of the event was also seen as a great opportunity to learn more first-hand about seed and Series A funding topics. Now, only a short time after the event, it is too early to tell if any deals have been closed and venture capital has been raised by the finalist startups due to the opportunities provided by EELISA Next Level. What is clear, however, is that the finalist startups:

- have expanded their network,
- have pitched in front of a jury of investors,
- have received feedback on their pitches and their business models,
- have been contacted before, during, and after the EELISA Next Level event by investors who were interested in the startups,
- have learned about seed and Series A funding from experts, investors, and startups who were already successful in raising seed or Series A funding,
- have had the opportunity to ask experts, investors, and successful startups anything they wanted to know about seed and Series A funding,
- could increase their visibility on the European VC investor scene,
- could profit from networking with startup consultants from 7 European countries, mainly German VC investors, and other European startups,
- have earned the distinction of being selected by the pre-selection jury as finalists for EELISA Next Level and, in the case of the winners of the investor pitch competition, of being selected by the jury of investors as winners of the EELISA Next Level Startup Awards.

We consider EELISA Next Level as a great success and would like to stress that such an event would not have been possible if it had involved only one EELISA partner institution. This is because every EELISA partner institution at any given short time period of an event like EELISA Next Level being offered would have only one or a few startups that are seeking seed or Series A funding of between 500,000 € and 5,000,000 € of such a high quality to be interesting for professional VC investors. Therefore, only by opening such an event to startups from all EELISA partners and by joining forces could a sufficient number of advanced startups be brought together to make it interesting for investors to attend the event at their own expense. Additionally,

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	<p>in some countries it is harder to find VC investors for startups than in others and by opening one EELISA partner's network of investors to startups from all EELISA partners clearly created new opportunities that without such an event would not have been possible. In sum, EELISA Next Level succeeded very well not only in creating value for the finalist startups, investors, and the other participants, but also in creating an added European value. EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event was made possible through the funding of the EELISA InnoCORE project.</p>
<p>Documentation of the event</p>	<p>A report on the first day of EELISA Next Level on the EELISA at FAU website including a video interview with Ariane Coletta, member of the EELISA Next Level Jury of Investors: https://www.eelisa.fau.de/2024/03/27/boosting-your-start-up-to-the-next-level/</p> <p>A report on the first day of EELISA Next Level on the EELISA website: https://eelisa.eu/boosting-your-start-up-to-the-next-level/</p>

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Table 14: Evaluation of “EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event” offered by FAU

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Annex I – Call for EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event

**Call for EELISA Next Level:
Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event**

**22 and 23 March 2024 at ZOLLHOF Tech
Incubator in Nürnberg, Germany**

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EELISA Next Level Event Webpage:
<https://www.eelisa.fau.de/eelisa-next-level/>

EELISA Next Level Application Webpage:
<https://www.eelisa.fau.de/eelisa-next-level-application/>

Call for EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event

If you believe your startup is among the top innovators within EELISA European University and you seek to secure seed or Series A funding, then you should definitely apply for “EELISA Next Level”, which will take place at ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator in Nuremberg, Germany, on 22 and 23 March 2024. EELISA Next Level is designed to be your seed and Series A funding booster, offering you both: pitch competition and networking event. Our network comprises top European incubators such as Station F in Paris, the largest startup campus in the world, or ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator, the fastest growing tech incubator in Germany (see the full list below) with their respective mentors, highly successful startups, and networks of investors.

Benefits

EELISA Next Level will not only give you the opportunity to pitch in front of investors, receive valuable feedback, and win the EELISA Next Level Startup Awards, but you will also participate in an exciting program that will give you the opportunity to expand your network, meet investors, learn from more experienced Series B and C startups, and help you to secure your seed or Series A funding to take your startup to the next level.

Eligibility

EELISA Next Level is open to all digital, tech, and deep tech startups (and spinoffs):

- who have already mastered the pre-seed phase of their entrepreneurship journey and are now seeking seed or Series A funding (approximately 500k – 5 million €)

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- from all EELISA institutions including startups founded by at least one alumnus or alumna of an EELISA institution and startups from the following incubators connected to EELISA institutions: actúaupm (UPM), BME U[S]3 (BME), Chimie Paris Innov (PSL), Incubateur Descartes (ENPC), Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL), Innovation Labs (UPB), ITU Cekirdek (ITU), ITU Genova (ITU), PC Up (PSL), Polo Tecnologico (SNS), Station F (ENPC), and ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU).

Funding

In case of being selected as a finalist for EELISA Next Level by the pre-selection jury, please contact your local EELISA office to ask about the possibility of receiving travel and subsistence support to attend the event. For those finalists who have to travel to EELISA Next Level from EELISA institutions other than FAU and who cannot receive funding from their local EELISA office, EELISA at FAU can offer a limited number of grants of 700 € per team member affiliated to UPM, ITU, UPB, SNS, SSSA, or one of the incubators connected to these institutions and 500 € per team member affiliated to PSL, ENPC, BME, or one of the incubators connected to these institutions with a maximum of two grants (i.e., 1,400 € or 1,000 €) per startup team. Startups from the FAU innovation ecosystem can only receive a grant of 350 € per team member with a maximum of two grants (700 €) per startup team if their startup is located outside the Nuremberg Metropolitan Region. You will know before the event if you can receive one of these grants which will only be paid after your on-site participation at EELISA Next Level from 22 to 23 March 2024.

Timeline

- Application Deadline: 31 January 2024
- Notification about Admission: No later than 9 February 2024
- "EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event": 22 and 23 March 2024

Evaluation criteria

The applications will be evaluated by a pre-selection jury composed of representatives from each EELISA member according to the following criteria on a scale from 1 (low) to 10 (high):

- Quality of the business model
- Level of the market potential
- Quality and complementarity of the team
- Scalability of the business model
- Track record and prospects of success

At EELISA Next Level the jury for the pitch competition will be composed of five investors. The jury will evaluate the startups according to the following criteria on a scale from 1 (low) to 10 (high):

- Quality of the business model
- Level of the market potential
- Quality and complementarity of the team
- Scalability of the business model
- Track record and prospects of success
- Quality of the pitch and responses in discussion

Application

Please use the EELISA Next Level [application webpage](#) to submit your application including a short investor pitch video of 30 seconds maximum and your investor pitch deck no later than 31 January 2024.

(Note: Your investor pitch deck must not exceed 10 slides plus cover page and together with the short investor pitch video of 30 seconds maximum should allow the pre-selection jury to

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form a judgement with regard to the evaluation criteria: quality of the business model; level of the market potential; quality and complementarity of the team; scalability of the business model; track record and prospects of success. The maximum file size for the investor pitch deck is 5 MB.)

EELISA Next Level is an entrepreneurship activity of the EELISA innoCORE project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

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